

CLASSIFICATION OF UZBEKISTAN TEXTS BASED ON BIDIRECTIONAL TRANSFORMER (BERT) ARCHITECTURE

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ABSTRACT

This article proposes a neural network architecture using the BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) model for sentiment analysis of Uzbek texts. The work uses data augmentation methods such as text preprocessing, stop word removal, stemming, and synonym substitution. The process of training a neural network using synthetic data is described. The effectiveness of the model is evaluated by accuracy, F1 score, and classification reports. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of BERT embeddings and data augmentation methods in sentiment analysis of Uzbek.

Introduction. In recent years, deep learning technologies in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) have yielded remarkable results as an important tool for analyzing and understanding texts. In particular, sentiment analysis, i.e. determining the positive, negative or neutral sentiment of a text, is widely used in marketing, social media monitoring and customer opinion analysis. The number of studies related to sentiment analysis in Uzbek is limited, and the available resources often consist of small amounts of unlabeled data. Therefore, data augmentation techniques are important for training and testing effective NLP models [1-4]. In this work, an embeddings layer of the BERT model and a neural network architecture built using Keras are proposed for sentiment analysis in Uzbek. In addition, synthetic data is created by pre-processing the texts (stemming, removing stop words) and replacing synonyms, which improves the learning capabilities of the model. The performance of the model is evaluated through classification accuracy, F1 score, and confusion matrix. In this way, a modern and effective approach for sentiment analysis in the Uzbek language is proposed [5-7].

Methodology

BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) is a bidirectional context-aware Transformer-based deep neural network model. It is mainly used to transform text into contextual embeddings (Figure 1).

1. Input Representation

The text fed to the BERT model is represented as follows:

$$\eta = 2 \cdot 10^{-5} X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

Each token is defined as a sum of three different embeddings:

$$e_i = e_i^{\text{token}} + e_i^{\text{segment}} + e_i^{\text{position}}$$

here

e_i^{token} — token embedding

e_i^{segment} — sentence segment embedding (A or B)

e_i^{position} — positional embedding

The result is the input matrix:

$$E = (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n) \quad n \times d$$

Figure 1. BERT architecture

2. Transformer Encoder Layers

The BERT model consists of Transformer encoder layers (for BERT-base, for BERT-large $L = 24$)

Each layer consists of the following two main components:

2.1 Multi-Head Self-Attention

The self-attention mechanism is defined as follows:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V$$

here:

$$Q = HW^Q - \text{Query}$$

$$K = HW^K - \text{Key}$$

$$V = HW^V - \text{Value}$$

Multi-head attention:

$$\text{MHA}(H) = \text{Concat}(\text{head}_1, \dots, \text{head}_h)W^O$$

$$\text{head}_i = \text{Attention}(Q_i, K_i, V_i)$$

2.2 Feed-Forward Network (FFN)

It is applied separately for each token:

$$\text{FFN}(x) = \max(0, xW_1 + b_1)W_2 + b_2$$

2.3 Residual coupling and normalization

For each sub-layer:

$$H^{(l)} = \text{LayerNorm}(H^{(l-1)} + \text{Sublayer}(H^{(l-1)}))$$

3. Bidirectional context modeling

The main advantage of BERT is that it takes into account context from both sides:

$$P(w_i | \dots, w_1, O, w_{i-1}, w_{i+1}, \dots, w_n)$$

This is different from traditional left-to-right or right-to-left models.

4. Special tokens

BERT uses the following special tokens:

[CLS] — whole sentence representation

[SEP] — sentence segmentation

[MASK] — token hidden during training

$$h_{\text{CLS}} = H^{(L)}[0]$$

In this study, a deep neural network and BERT embeddings integration was used for sentiment analysis of Uzbek texts.

Results

In this study, a neural network model based on BERT embeddings and Keras was used for sentiment analysis of Uzbek texts. 450 synthetic text samples were used during model training, with 150 samples for each sentiment class (negative, neutral, positive). The data was divided into training and validation sets in a ratio of 80:20. During the training process, the validation accuracy of the model reached 0.7667. The loss function of the model was 0.8981 in the last epoch, which indicates that the model was stably optimized during training and the risk of overfitting was low.

The evaluation results of the model in the validation set were as follows (Table 1):

Table 1

Model evaluation results on the validation set

Class	Precision	Coverage (Recall)	F1 score	Sample number
Negative (0)	0.73	0.63	0.68	30
Neutral (1)	0.71	0.90	0.79	30
Positive (2)	0.88	0.77	0.82	30

Overall accuracy: 0.7667. Weighted F1 score: 0.7647. The results show that the model performs relatively well in the negative and positive classes, while the neutral class performs strongly in terms of recall. This indicates that the class balance is effective when working with synthetic data. The following observations were also made through confusion matrix analysis (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Confusion matrix

Of the 30 negative class samples, 19 were correctly classified, while 11 were incorrectly classified into other classes. Of the 30 neutral class samples, 27 were correctly identified, which is explained by the high recall. Of the 30 positive class samples, 23 were correctly classified. Overall, the results confirm that it is possible to build an efficient and robust model for sentiment analysis in Uzbek using BERT embeddings and data augmentation.

Conclusion

In this study, a classification model based on BERT embeddings and artificial neural networks was developed to perform sentiment analysis for Uzbek texts. The proposed approach used pre-processing of texts, removal of stop words, stemming, and data augmentation based on synonyms. This allowed us to significantly enrich the small initial data set and ensure class balance. The experimental results showed that the model achieved an accuracy of 0.76 and an F1 index of about 0.76. In particular, the model demonstrated high efficiency in identifying positive and neutral classes. At the same time, some misclassifications were observed in the negative class, which indicates the need for further improvement of the model in the future. The obtained results confirm that the BERT embeddings and data augmentation methods are effective for sentiment analysis in Uzbek. In the future, it is desirable to use large-scale real datasets, fully fine-tune the transformer model, and apply deep multi-layer architectures to further develop the research.

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